

Thought-Provoking Blend of Theory and Practice

Amazon Book Review Series of “*Better Economics for the Earth: A Lesson from Quantum and Information Theories*”

Ricardo, Big Berd, & AJ

December 26, 2024

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Blend of theory and practice!

This book is a refreshing take on economic theory, drawing inspiration from quantum mechanics and information science. Real-life examples ground its theoretical framework, showing how small changes in economic approaches can lead to meaningful environmental benefits. This book encourages readers to question long-standing assumptions and consider broader social and ecological impacts when defining economic progress.

Ricardo

★★★★★ Blend of theory and practice !

Reviewed in the United States on December 26, 2024

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Helpful

Report

BigBerd

★★★★★ Ecological Economics

Reviewed in the United States on December 26, 2024

If only more people would think this way! Such a great book. It really made me stop and think.

Helpful

Report

AJ

★★★★★ Thought-provoking

Reviewed in the United States on December 26, 2024

This book offers a thought-provoking exploration of how modern economic systems intersect with environmental sustainability. Drawing on information theory, the book challenges traditional economic models, arguing for a holistic approach that incorporates ecological and technological factors. The authors present a compelling case for reevaluating the relationship between economic growth and planetary health, proposing solutions that prioritize long-term stability over short-term gain.

Screenshot. Review of “*Better Economics for the Earth*” by Ricardo, Berd, and AJ [1-3].

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Ecological Economics

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Thought-provoking

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(*) Note: This paper reprints Ricardo's, Berd's, and AJ's reviews [1-3] appearing on the Amazon page of the title [4].

References

- [1] Ricardo. (2024, Dec. 26). Blend of theory and practice!. <https://www.amazon.com/gp/customer-reviews/R1XR6GT4U8YK6U/>
- [2] Berd, B. (2024, Dec. 26). Ecological Economics. <https://www.amazon.com/gp/customer-reviews/R5OUC5XFY60G1/>
- [3] AJ. (2024, Dec. 26). Thought-provoking. <https://www.amazon.com/gp/customer-reviews/R2NQHC74VPY8BP/>
- [4] Vuong, Q. H. & Nguyen, M. H. (2024). *Better Economics for the Earth: A Lesson from Quantum and Information Theories*. <https://www.amazon.com/dp/B0D98L5K44>